

MSc Geo-information Science and Remote sensing

Academic Internship Report – GRS70424

Monitoring water surface of agricultural reservoirs in semi-arid regions using multi-spectral remote sensing

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«Εἰς μὲν τὸν πατέρα μου ὀφείλω τὸ ζῆν,
εἰς δὲ τὸν διδάσκαλόν μου τὸ εὖ ζῆν»

– Alexander the Great 338 BCE: I am indebted to my father for living, but to my teacher for living well (For his father Philip II and his teacher Aristotle).

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Abstract

This academic internship focused on addressing the gap in understanding water dynamics in small-sized agricultural reservoirs in semi-arid regions. Using Sentinel-2 multispectral remote sensing data, the study aimed to estimate water surface levels over the period 2017 – 2023 and analyze filling and discharge patterns in two reservoirs in Tunisia (Lebna watershed) and three in India (Berambadi watershed). The research investigated how a multitude of spectral indices, including Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI) and Multi-Band Water Index (MBWI), the Sentinel Water Index (SWI), and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), could be utilized to quantify uncertainty in water surface estimation and leverage the multi-temporal frequency of Sentinel-2 to characterize recharge and discharge patterns. The study employed six frequently used indices and assessed their performance against ground data for single-day observations and temporal scales. A Locally Estimated Scatter Plot Smoothing (LOESS) algorithm was applied to determine minimal and maximal surfaces between seasons by comparing indices LOESS to ground data LOESS for accuracy in estimating seasonal patterns. The study revealed suboptimal accuracy in actual surface estimation, and the attempt to use multiple indices to quantify uncertainty for small reservoirs was unsuccessful. However, the identification of seasonal patterns proved feasible, demonstrating the potential of this methodology in understanding interseasonal charge and discharge patterns in small reservoirs. Further analysis is needed to validate these findings across a larger number of test sites and temporal scales.

Keywords: Remote sensing, Multi-spectral water indices, Small reservoirs, Tunisia, India

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWEI	Automated Water Extraction Index
CNES	Centre national d'études spatiales
DGPS	Differential Global Positioning System
IRD	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
HSRI	High Spatial Resolution Image
LISAH	Laboratoire d'Etude des Interactions entre Sol-Agrosystème-Hydrosystème
MNDWI	Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
MBWI	Multi-Band Water Index
MSI	Multi-Spectral Instrument
ND	Normalized Difference
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
RS	Remote Sensing
SWI	Sentinel Water Index
SWIR	Short Wave Infrared
SD	Standard Deviation
UMR	Unité mixte de recherche
VNIR	Visible and Near Infrared

1 Introduction

1.1 Internship organization background

This 6-month academic internship was conducted under the supervision of the Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (IRD), a French public research institution jointly overseen by the French Ministries of Higher Education and Research and Foreign Affairs. Operating internationally from its headquarters in Marseille, and metropolitan centres in Montpellier and Bondy, IRD serves three primary missions: research on global development, overseas consultancy, and training. The institute engages in scientific programs that contribute to the sustainable development of countries in the Global South and in the French overseas territories, with a focus on the interplay between human activities and the environment.

In the context of this internship, IRD had the role of the parent company/institution, and I contributed to the MonStockDO project. MonStockDO is a scientific project coordinated by IRD, involving INRAE, IRD and CNES (Centre national d'études spatiales) researches, and funding by the CNES. MonStockDO aims to assess data acquired by the Sentinel-2 and Venùs satellites for monitoring water stocks in small agricultural reservoirs fed by runoff and rivers across three study sites: Lebna watershed in Tunisia, Berambadi watershed in India, and Aude basin in France. The internship is hosted at the Unité mixte de recherche (UMR) – Laboratoire d'Etude des Interactions entre Sol-Agrosystème-Hydrosystème (LISAH, Laboratory for the study of Interactions between Soil-Agro-Hydro systems). UMR LISAH is a collaborative research unit supervised by INRAE (National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment), IRD, and the Institute Agro, and it is also a contracted unit of AgroParisTech. The laboratory is situated in Montpellier, Occitania, France.

1.2 Context and justification of research

1.2.1 Small reservoirs

Small reservoirs are water storage structures designed to capture and store water below 10^6 m³ or a surface area typically less than 50 ha (Owusu et al., 2022). They are typically constructed in local or rural areas to address various water-related needs and can be found in many places around world in great numbers (Figure 1). Small reservoirs serve multiple purposes, including: irrigation, domestic water supply, livestock watering, erosion control and flood control. In the effort to meet the water needs of rural smallholders, the use of small reservoirs emerges as a promising solution, showing significant potential for supporting small-scale irrigation (Wisser et al., 2010). Unlike larger projects such as extensive irrigation and dams, these reservoirs have fewer environmental impacts, gaining sustained attention and support from donors and stakeholders.

Figure 1: Estimated number of small reservoirs for several countries from (Ogilvie et al., 2016)

Numerous studies conducted in different countries highlight the various benefits of these multi-use systems but also note limitations in agricultural production (Khlifi et al., 2010; Mugabe et al., 2003). The inherent features of these systems, characterized by their small scale, scattered distribution, and isolation, present challenges for widespread resource monitoring. Additionally, modelling faces considerable uncertainties, primarily due to highly spatial confined rainfall intensities that conventional field observations or satellite-based products fail to detect. Despite the increasing prevalence of small reservoirs and other water conservation efforts in semi-arid areas, their hydrological potential remains largely unknown, marked by significant variations in functionality due to diverse catchment and reservoir characteristics (Ogilvie, 2016).

Understanding charge and discharge patterns becomes of great importance for water management in the absence of ground monitoring systems, especially amid changing climatic conditions (Carlier et al., 2016; Habets et al., 2018). However, the installation and maintenance of a hydrometric observation network demand substantial resources, rendering them incompatible with the localized and modest importance of small reservoirs in the water budget (Liebe et al., 2005).

1.2.2 Use of multispectral Remote Sensing (RS) in water mapping

To combat the difficulty in monitoring small reservoirs, multispectral Remote Sensing (RS) water detection has shown great potential to water detection and water surface mapping (Cordeiro et al., 2021; Huang et al., 2018), although most studies focus on larger reservoirs and smaller reservoirs have been largely neglected. Despite that, Ogilvie (2016) highlighted the potential of freely available medium-resolution imagery (Landsat) for monitoring gauged small reservoirs as low as 1 hectare. However, extending this approach to multiple ungauged small reservoirs presents challenges in terms of identification, automation, and converting surface area to volumes without lake-specific rating curves¹.

Figure 2: Reflection of different land uses for the spectrum range 0.4 to 2 μm (extracted form USGS Spectroscopy Lab)

Different wavelengths of the optical spectrum interact uniquely with water, revealing distinct spectral signatures crucial for RS applications. Figure 2 shows that in the visible spectrum (400-700 nm), water absorbs minimal energy. Near-InfraRed (NIR) wavelengths (700-1400 nm) experience lower reflectance in water due to molecular absorption characteristics. However, water absorbs strongly all of the radiation in the Short Wave Infrared (SWIR) region (1400-3000 nm) because of overtone vibrations of water molecules. While calm water (clear) show the above pattern turbulent water (with suspended sediment) does not follow the same pattern and have higher reflectance values due to the interference of trapped sediment. Similarly water that is covered with aquatic vegetation or produce glint has a total different spectral signature from clear calm water. These interactions are pivotal for designing spectral indices that exploit the different responses across the spectrum to detect and map water bodies in optical RS imagery.

RS water mapping through spectral indices stands leverage the unique reflective properties of water across different wavelengths, enabling precise identification and delineation of water bodies without

¹ The rating curve is a relation between stage (river level) and streamflow (discharge). Each stream channel is different and, because the stage-discharge relation is a function of the streambed material and geometry, each rating curve will be unique to that site and a particular period of time.

invasive measures (Xu, 2006). Fisher et al. (2016) noted that this inexpensive approach proves particularly valuable for large-scale applications, offering a cost-effective and scalable solution for monitoring water resources on regional or global scales. The near real-time monitoring capabilities of spectral indices contribute to understanding dynamic changes in water bodies, facilitating timely responses to emergencies and supporting informed decision-making in water resource planning. Continuous advancements in satellite technology, including high-resolution imagery and improved spatial and temporal resolution, further enhance the accuracy and applicability of spectral indices in water mapping. In addition water mapping by thresholding spectral indices is a simple and computational light process especially for time series analysis (H. Jiang et al., 2014). For this study multiple spectral indices were employed and are explained in 2.4.2 Spectral indices.

1.3 The aim of internship research

This research project aims to fill a critical gap in understanding water dynamics in agricultural water reservoirs, particularly focusing on small-sized reservoirs in semi-arid regions. Utilizing multispectral RS data, the study aimed to 1) estimate the water surface over reservoirs along 5 years based on Sentinel-2 time-series images and 2) analyse the filling and discharge patterns. The insights gained from this endeavour might be invaluable for comprehending water availability and usage patterns, offering crucial support for sustainable development at both regional and national levels.

For policymakers, water managers, and farmers relying on these reservoirs for sediment trapping, groundwater recharge and irrigation, the findings hold profound importance. By leveraging the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of RS (Willis, 2015), this project not only addresses the research gap but also contributes essential information for the development of effective water resource management strategies in semi-arid regions. Ultimately, bridging this knowledge gap is crucial for advancing scientific understanding and facilitating sustainable water management practices in these environments.

1.4 Research objective and research questions

The objective of this research project is to create water surface maps for pilot small agricultural reservoirs for two semi-arid case studies, spanning the years 2017 to 2023, employing Sentinel-2 time series data. The methodology involves the application of various water detection spectral indices detailed in section 2.4.2 Spectral indices. This multispectral RS approach is not only cost-effective but also efficient, generating multi-temporal maps essential for analysing reservoir filling and discharge processes. The analysis will be facilitated and validated using field data previously collected by other researchers.

Research questions:

1. How can the multitude of spectral indices be employed to quantify the uncertainty associated with water surface estimation in the context of remote sensing water detection?
2. How can the multi-temporal frequency of Sentinel-2 can be leveraged to characterize recharge and discharge patterns?

2. Data and Methods

2.1 Study areas

The research will focus on the Lebna catchment in Tunisia (Figure 3) and Berambadi catchment in India (Figure 4). Both sites are characterized by high variability of surface landscape properties and they have differences in terms of climate, agriculture, and pedologic contexts.

The Lebna watershed, situated in the Nabeul *governorate* (province) of Tunisia (Figure 3), spans an area of 218 km². This region demonstrates a humid Mediterranean climate in its upstream areas, gradually transitioning to a semi-arid climate downstream. Moreover, the Lebna catchment is characterized by rugged terrain, featuring a maximum elevation difference of approximately 600 m. The catchment area experiences an average annual rainfall of 650 mm, coupled with a potential evapotranspiration of 1,200 mm (INM, 1999).

Figure 3: Lebna watershed in Tunisia with the 12 reservoirs at maximum extend including their IDs.

Within this landscape, there are 12 reservoirs, varying in size from 1 ha (El Hajia reservoir) to 720 ha (Lebna reservoir), with an average size of around 50 hectares and a median size of 5 hectares, additional information for the reservoirs can be find in Table 16 of the Appendix. These reservoirs possess depths ranging from a few meters to approximately 20 meters. Notably, while some reservoirs in the region may dry during summer periods, the Lebna reservoir, being the largest in size (Table 1) remains resilient and never dry out in the summer.

The primary purposes of these reservoirs are irrigation and sediment trapping. Additionally, they mitigating erosion, spawn fish production and promoting aquatic biodiversity. In addition, may

contribute to enhancing groundwater recharge. In this internship results were created for all reservoirs but considering the available ground data and for the propose of this academic report two reservoirs from Lebna site were selected to be analysed in detail. The Lebna reservoir, being the largest in size, can offer general insights to the surrounding reservoirs and serve as a reference of the analysis while, Kamech, being a typical small reservoir, complements the understanding of small reservoirs(Table 1).

Table 1: Lebna reservoirs that were studied, and their maximum extent.

ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)
1	Lebna	720
10	Kamech	4.8

Figure 4: Berambadi watershed in India with reservoirs at maximum extend including their IDs.

The Berambadi watershed, covering an expanse of 84 km², situated in the state of Karnataka, India (Figure 4). This region is characterized by a sub-humid to semi-arid tropical climate, featuring an annual rainfall of 900 mm in the upstream (West) and 700 mm downstream (East) (Sekhar et al., 2016). The climatic conditions of the monsoon dynamics drive three main seasons: dry season (winter in January and February, summer from March to May), Kharif (South-West monsoon season, from June to September) and Rabi (North-East monsoon season, from October to December).

The topography of the area is characterized by a smooth terrain with a small (North-East) slope, a median altitude of 900 m and a maximum elevation difference of approximately 150 m. There are 39 water reservoirs existing along the hydrographic network within the Berambadi watershed, while there are an additional 13 reservoirs located outside the Berambadi watershed (Figure 4). They are

called “tanks” in India. The reservoirs were built in depressions to collect rainwater initially for domestic use and to water the herds or in chains along the watercourses initially to irrigate agricultural plots downstream by a system of channels (Gomez et al., 2021). Additionally, these reservoirs serve various additional purposes for the local population, including drinking water, irrigation, fish production, washing, and bathing. These reservoirs range from 0.1 ha to 48 ha of maximal surface (with an average of 2.97 ha and a median of 0.68 ha) while exhibiting shallow depths. For the same reasons to the previous study area, 3 reservoirs were selected for a deep analysis, namely Berambadi Dam, Berambadi Temple Tank and Kannegala River Tank (Table 2) although results were produced for all 52 reservoirs (Table 17 of the Appendix).

Table 2: Berambadi reservoirs that were studied, and their maximum size.

ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)
2	Berambadi Dam	47.94
8	Berambadi Temple Tank	2.47
13	Kannegala River Tank	8.87

2.2 Ground Data

Ground data related to water surface, presented in CSV format, were supplied by my supervisors from IRD’s database. These dataset were used to analyse the water surface estimated by remote sensing.

2.2.1 Lebna

On the Lebna watershed, the ground data are available for the Lebna and Kamech reservoirs (Table 1). Data are daily values of water height, area and volume from 2010 to 2023. These data come from observations of water heights recorded by pressure sensors and controlled by varied field operators. Daily values of reservoirs' volume and surface have been estimated using reservoir area-capacity equation or rating curves. These rating curves were derived from the reservoir morphology measured by bathymetric and topographic campaigns. For the purpose of this study only the water surface was used for validation purposes. For the Kamech reservoir, ground truth data is corrupted since 2022-10-24 until 2023-05-14 (sensor failure) and missing onwards.

2.2.2 Berambadi

The Berambadi watershed ground data are composed of water height measured by Differential Global Positioning System (DGPS). The measurements of water height pertain to three reservoirs within the watershed. Those are Berambadi Dam, Berambadi Temple Tank and Kannegala River Tank (located on Figure 2). The measurement sare collected twice a month by IRD partners in India. The temporal span of this dataset initiates in January 2023 and extends through September 2023.

2.3 Remote sensing data

2.3.1 Multispectral remote sensing data

The multispectral RS data utilized in this study comprise a series of Sentinel-2 optical images covering the two designated study areas over a span of five years, ranging from January 2017 to September 2023.

The decision to use Sentinel 2 images were made as is freely available optical satellite covering both sites with good spatial and temporal resolution. The two twin satellites Sentinel 2A and 2B have a combined constellation revisit is 5 days while the revisit frequency of each single satellite is 10 days. The sensor onboard of Sentinel 2 is the MultiSpectral Instrument (MSI) and has different spatial and radiometric resolution for different bands. From the 13 bands, 3 band (1, 9 and 10) are used mainly for atmospheric analysis and correction thus removed from the indices analysis. Bands that had 20 m resolution was resampled to 10 m in order to be the same with the rest bands. Bellow table provide more information about the bands.

Table 3: Sentinel 2 spectral overview, adapted from MSI Technical Guide. In grey are highlighted the unused spectral bands at 60m of spatial resolution.

Band Number and Description	Spatial resolution (m)	Central wavelength (nm)	Bandwidth (nm)
1 (Coastal and Aerosol)	60	442.7	20
2 (Blue)	10	492.7	65
3 (Green)	10	559.8	35
4 (Red)	10	664.6	30
5	20	704.1	14
6	20	740.5	14
7	20	782.8	19
8	10	832.8	105
8a	20	864.7	21
9	60	945.1	19
10	60	1373.5	29
11	20	1613.7	90
12	20	2202.4	174

In particular, the analysis focused on level 2 data (L2A) acquired from Copernicus. Images that were initially available only as level 1 (L1C) underwent atmospheric correction to L2A using the Sen2Cor (Pignatale, 2022) application. The selection of images involved an automated download procedure using sen2r (Ranghetti et al., 2020) an Application Programming Interface (API) for automated download of Sentinel images in R programming language. The image selection was determined by examining the accompanying metadata, and only those images with a global (tile) cloud cover threshold of less than 10% were downloaded. This procedure took place for both Lebna and Berambadi sites. In order to minimize temporal observation gaps, additional images for the

Lebna site were manually downloaded, surpassing the global threshold of 10%. These images were specifically chosen as they were deemed to be cloud-free within the extent of the study area. The original idea was to apply the same manual technique to the Berambadi site. However, time constraints prevented the implementation of this step and thus Berambadi dataset has more data gaps. A comprehensive exposition of data acquisition and processing procedures is available in section 2.4.1 Data preprocessing.

In total 230 images were downloaded from 2017-01-01 to 2023-09-22 over the Lebna catchment (Table 4). The limited observations during the months from October to January can be attributed to the cloudy and rainy winter conditions typical of the Mediterranean climate at this time of the year. Similarly the clear days of Mediterranean summer provide many cloud free day during July and August.

Table 4: Lebna site Sentinel-2 images description and images availability per month.

Dates: 2017-01-01 to 2023-09-22				
Orbit / Tile:	122 / 32 SPF	Number of Images / Month	Number of Months	Period
Total images	230	0	7	Oct – Jan
Platform	Images	1	15	
2A	123	2	19	
2B	107	3	16	Jul – Aug
Level	Images	4	13	
L1C	41	≥ 5	14	
L2A	189			
Download	Images			
Manual	19			
Automated	211			

In total 259 images were downloaded from 2017-01-01 to 2023-09-22 over the Berambadi catchment (Table 5). Despite the higher susceptibility to cloudy weather in the Berambadi region (monsoons), it exhibits more near-cloud-free observations compared to Lebna. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that the Berambadi site falls within the coverage of two satellite orbits, resulting in more frequent passes and increased chances of clear skies. Additionally, it is evident that there are numerous months with either no observations or only one observation. This pattern is a consequence of the tropical monsoons affecting India from July to December. Consequently, the dry period from January to May sees very few cloudy/rainy days, leading to more available observations.

Table 5: Berambadi site Sentinel-2 images description and images availability per month

Dates: 2017-01-01 to 2023-09-22				
Orbit / Tile:	19 & 62	Images / Month	Months	Period
Total images	259	0	25	Jun – Sep
Platform	Images	1	11	
2A	130	2	3	Oct – Apr
2B	129	3	9	
Level	Images	4	3	
L1C	114	≥ 5	29	
L2A	145			
Download	Images			
Manual	0			
Automated	259			

2.3.2 Reservoirs boundaries

2.3.2.1 Maximal extend of water surface

Over the Lebna catchment, the maximal extend of each reservoir underwent manual digitization utilizing ESRI's World Imagery basemap, which had a spatial resolution of 1.2 m at the site. Conversely, the maximal extend of each reservoir over the Berambadi site had already been digitized in previous studies based on CNES Pléiades data and was provided by IRD for this research. It is important to highlight that, unlike Lebna, the flat morphology of Berambadi's reservoirs results makes maximal extend determination difficult.

2.3.2.2 Water surface determination by Google Earth images

To further validate the correspondence between RS water surface data and ground measurements, certain reservoirs underwent manual digitization with high spatial resolution RS images. Specifically, at the Lebna site, two reservoirs with ground data were manually digitized utilizing images obtained from Google Earth Pro's "historic imagery" tool. In total, three images were used for the Lebna reservoir, and six images were used for the Kamech reservoir (Table 6). The decision to select fewer images for Lebna reservoir was made 1) due to lack of time to review a larger reservoir and 2) because the main focus of this study was the small reservoirs. The images were attributed to the Maxar WorldView-4 satellite, formerly known as GeoEye-2, which offers a panchromatic image with a spatial resolution of 31 cm and CNES Pléiades with panchromatic image of 50 cm spatial resolution. Validation images was to be acquired with the same approach for Berambadi site but there was not sufficient time.

Table 6: Dates selected for reservoirs boundaries mapping of Lebna and Kamech reservoirs.

Dates for Lebna	Dates for Kamech
2017-08-30	2017-08-30
2019-03-12	2017-10-10
2020-04-08	2018-07-25
	2019-03-12
	2021-10-03
	2022-04-08

2.4 Methods

This section will describe the methods used to address each research question (Figure 5). The general direction of the methodology starts with the data acquisition and preprocessing followed by the calculation of the indices, the comparison of each index and lastly the estimation of seasonal patterns while comparing the ground data. For each research question, specific methods were employed considering the data sources and analysis techniques involved.

Figure 5: Flowchart of the methodology

2.4.1 Data preprocessing

To gather a sufficient number of RS images covering the 5-year period from 2017 to 2023 for two sites, an API tool was deemed necessary. Given the intention to conduct all analyses in R using the R Studio Integrated Development Environment (IDE), the choice was made to employ sen2r (Ranghetti et al., 2020). This API facilitated the search of metadata available on the Copernicus Open Access Hub, identifying and marking images for download based on specific criteria. The criteria included the designated tile and orbit for the two sites, the maximum acceptable cloud cover, and the selection of only level 2 data. In instances where level 2 data were unavailable, the approach involved downloading and converting level 1 data to level 2 using Sen2Cor (Pignatale, 2022). This strategy proved successful, and for instances requiring manual date selection to fill gaps (only Lebna site), images were manually chosen by searching through the Copernicus Browser. In

cases where only level 1 data were available, they were downloaded and converted using sen2cor in a similar manner. Sen2r provided an added advantage by automatically cropping the image to Areas Of Interest (AOI) and stacking the downloaded images, consolidating all spectral bands into a single TIF file to be used in the subsequent steps of the analysis. A detailed overview of the characteristics of the downloaded images can be found in Table 4 and 5. Additionally, a TIF file containing only Band 1, which was utilized for cloud detection was created. Band 1 pixels with a value exceeding the values of 1,500 for a given date were classified as clouds. If clouds were found in a specific reservoir for a specific day then this date was dedicated from the analysis of this reservoir.

2.4.2 Spectral indices

As was mentioned in the introduction RS spectral indices frequently used by bibliography are useful tools to detect and monitor water (Khalid et al., 2021; Tesfaye & Breuer, 2023). In this section, four spectral indices commonly used in many studies were selected: Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI), Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI), Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI) and Multi-Band Water Index (MBWI). In addition, the Sentinel Water Index (SWI), which is a recent spectral index that is not yet utilized extensively, and the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) that is dedicated to the water detection were also tested.

It is important to note at this juncture that many spectral indices techniques typically require considerable time to define threshold values for each area or time period (Acharya et al., 2018). However, due to time constraints in this study and the primary goal of understanding the overall performance of the indices rather than achieving maximum accuracy, such approaches were not employed. Instead, a threshold of above 0 for the water detection indices (as dictated by the proposed authors) and similarly a threshold below 0 for NDVI was selected.

2.4.2.1 Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

While primarily designed for vegetation monitoring, NDVI, proposed by (Kriegler et al., 1969), can also be employed for water detection due to its sensitivity to changes in land cover. Meaning it can be used also to detect aquatic vegetation although due to lack of time this mechanic of NDVI was not researched. The formula for NDVI is:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red}$$

Where the NIR and red bands correspond to B8 and B4, respectively, for Sentinel-2. Negative NDVI values are indicative of water, making this index useful for water detection alongside its primary application in vegetation analysis (Gandhi et al., 2015).

2.4.2.2 Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)

NDWI is a widely used index designed to highlight water bodies in RS optical imagery. Published by both (Gao, 1996) and (McFeeters, 1996), NDWI is a slight modification of NDVI that utilizes the contrast between the absorption features of water in the NIR and Green bands. The formula is expressed as follows:

$$NDWI = \frac{Green - NIR}{Green + NIR}$$

Where the NIR and green bands correspond to B8 and B3, respectively, for Sentinel-2. The positive values produced by NDWI showcase water features, making it effective for water detection in various landscapes (Gao, 1996).

2.4.2.3 Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI)

Modified NDWI (MNDWI) is an adaptation of NDWI with modifications to optimize water and enhance open water features while efficiently suppressing and even removing built-up land noise as well as vegetation and soil noise. (Xu, 2006) proposed this index by replacing the NIR band in NDWI with the SWIR band, aiming to minimize the impact of water containments for better water detection results. The formula is expressed as follows:

$$MNDWI = \frac{Green - SWIR}{Green + SWIR}$$

Where the SWIR and green bands correspond to B11 and B3, respectively, for Sentinel-2. As a result, water features have positive values and thus are enhanced, while vegetation and soil usually have zero or negative values and therefore are suppressed. Although this effect can be considered beneficial, it can also lead to underestimations of turbid or shallow water surfaces (Singh et al., 2015).

2.4.2.4 Sentinel Water Index (SWI)

The Sentinel Water Index (SWI) is a relatively recent water detection index introduced by (W. Jiang et al., 2020). It shares a design similarity with the MNDWI, but instead of using the Green band, it utilizes the VNIR band. This modification enhances its ability to differentiate urban areas, sediment, salt, and ice from water bodies, exhibiting improved performance. SWI is particularly effective for turbid and shallow waters. Despite its promising potential, it currently lacks widespread uses in literature. The formula for SWI is:

$$SWI = \frac{VNIR - SWIR}{VNIR + SWIR}$$

Where the VNIR and SWIR bands correspond to B5 and B11, respectively for Sentinel-2.

2.4.2.5 Multi-Band Water Index (MBWI)

Previous indices that utilizing only two-bands have difficulties to accurately distinguish water in complex environments that include build-up areas, dark surfaces or mountain shadows (Feyisa et al., 2014; Wieland & Martinis, 2019). MBWI is a multi band index developed by (Wang et al., 2018) to maximize the spectral difference between water and non-water surfaces for Landsat 8, especially for mixed backgrounds like mountainous shadows and dark built-up areas. The formula for MBWI is expressed as:

$$MBWI = 2 \times Green - Red - NIR - SWIR_1 - SWIR_2$$

Adapted to Sentinel-2, the formula is as follows:

$$MBWI = 2 \times B3 - B4 - B8 - B11 - B12$$

As Landsat 8 Operational Land Imager (OLI)'s sensor has different characteristics for each spectral band than Sentinel-2 MSI's the results of MBWI are prone to small errors. In addition, this index is parametric and can be parameterized for individual uses but has not been parameterized in this study.

2.4.2.6 Automated Water Extraction Index (AWEI)

AWEI, proposed by (Feyisa et al., 2014) is another multi band index that integrates multiple bands to improve water detection accuracy, especially in areas that include shadow and dark surfaces that other classification methods often fail to classify correctly. The formula for AWEI is:

$$AWEI = 4 \times (Green - SWIR_1) \times (0.25 \times NIR + 2.75 \times SWIR_2)$$

Adapted to Sentinel-2, the formula is as follows:

$$AWEI = 4 \times (B3 - B11) \times (0.25 \times B8 + 2.75 \times B12)$$

AWEI incorporates coefficients to adjust band contributions, enhancing its performance in diverse landscapes, including regions with significant vegetation cover (Feyisa et al., 2014).

The following table summarizes the indices based on the parameterization, design and frequency in literature.

Table 7: Table of spectral indices

Spectral Index	Non parametric	Dedicated for water detection	Used in literature for water identification	Notes
NDVI	✓	✗	✓	Can detect aquatic vegetation blooms
NDWI	✓	✓	✓	Similar to NDVI but more sensitive to water
MNDWI	✓	✓	✓	Based on NDWI
SWI	✓	✓	✗	Used in only one scientific paper
MBWI	✗	✓	✓*	* Designed for Landsat
AWWEI	✗	✓	✓*	* Designed for Landsat

2.4.3 Indices calculation and water surface estimation

Indices were computed in R programming language from image TIF files containing all the spectral bands. Each index was computed based on the corresponding formula for the same image, and this procedure was repeated for all images.

After gathering all the products, the subsequent step involved estimating the water surface for the designated reservoirs on specific dates. This was achieved by counting all pixels within the reservoir's extent that had a value above the specified threshold. To address errors arising from changes in the reservoir's extent, a buffer of 15 meters was applied to all reservoirs except for Lebna (the largest) reservoir, where the buffer was extended to 50 meters. Pixel counts were then converted to hectares (each pixel being 100 m²).

The final step of the analysis involved a two-fold validation process, combining visual and statistical approaches. This validation had two main aspects: one focused on individual observations and another on the temporal scale.

For the individual observations, an assessment of the normalized error between the high-resolution manual digitization and the indices compared with the ground data surface was conducted. This aimed to gauge the effectiveness of the indices and ground data surface. Further investigation into dates displaying significant variations through spectral analysis was done to comprehend the dynamics and response of the indices. Due to time constraints, this analysis was limited to the Lebna site.

On the temporal scale, statistical tools including R², RMSE, and Bias were computed. These metrics were instrumental in providing an overarching evaluation of the indices, to answer the question of whether different indices could be regarded as sources of uncertainty in estimating water surfaces. However, it's worth noting that this analysis was constrained in the Lebna site due to the absence of water surface data for Berambadi.

2.4.4 Estimate of seasonal patterns

To estimate seasonal patterns, a mechanism was required to identify seasonal minimums and maximums while also cleaning or smoothing the signal. Additionally, this needed to be applied to all indices and ground data to compare seasonal results. To achieve this goal, a smoothing mechanism was selected. Locally Estimated Scatter Plot Smoothing (LOESS) was employed to create a local regression, allowing for a more nuanced understanding of the data trends. The loess function of stats-package {stats} in r language was used with the parameter of span = 0.15 selected by visual estimation.

Following this, the calculation of local extremes, both seasonal minimum and maximum values, was carried out within the LOESS framework. This was achieved by using a moving window of 4 points that tested when the current ascending or descending values stopped, labeling it as a local extreme. The resulting Min and Max values derived from this local regression were then compared with the corresponding values obtained from ground data LOESS. This approach facilitated an assessment of the local trends and extremities, providing insights into the relationship between the modeled regression and the seasonal patterns observed by the ground data.

2.4.5 Problems encountered/limitations and subsequent adaptations

During this internship, various challenges were encountered, with the primary issue revolving around time limitations. In the initial phase, there was consideration for utilizing both Sentinel-2 and Venϋs satellites. Venϋs, being a high spatial and high temporal optical satellite, had the potential to yield better and more frequent results. However, despite downloading the Venus satellite images, the data were not analysed within the given time frame. Another option involved the use of the Surf Water tool (Peña-Luque et al., 2021), an algorithm leveraging both Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-1 for creating a water surface time series estimation. Due to the necessity for collaboration with CNES, there was insufficient time to plan and execute the procedure. Furthermore, the tool is proprietary and lacks public documentation of its detailed steps. CNES also suggested adjusting water detection to incorporate Venϋs data instead of Sentinel-2. The Water Detect tool (Cordeiro et al., 2021), a CNES unsupervised multidimensional hierarchical clustering algorithm, was proposed for this purpose. Despite initial considerations, it was deemed more prudent to initiate the analysis with a simpler indices analysis before progressing to a more complicated approach. The iterative communication and data acquisition for Sentinel-2 were time-consuming, leading the analysis to focus more on the Lebna site and work exclusively with indices for water detection.

3. Results

3.1 Water surface estimation analysis at single dates

The water surface was first estimated at specific dates, based on the 6 spectral indices presented in section 2.4.2 Spectral indices. The dates correspond to the ones for which we a water surface estimated by Google Earth analysis (3 dates for the Lebna reservoir and 6 dates for the Kamech reservoir, Table 6). Then the water surface estimated by the spectral indices was compared to the one estimated by Google Earth analysis at each date (Figure 6).

Figure 6: WorldView-4, Sentinel-2, and the MNDWI images of Lebna

Differences of water surfaces measured on the ground and the ones and by Google Earth analysis over the Lebna Reservoir range from -0.34% to -5.5% (Table 8). And differences of water surfaces by spectral indices and by GoogleEarth analysis over the Lebna reservoir range from 0.73% to 8.65% (5.24 ha to 62.27 ha, Table 18 of the Appendix). Considering the water surfaces estimated by by Google Earth analysis as a “reference”, the uncertainties of ground measurements and spectral indices belong to similar ranges.

For the first two dates (2017-08-30 and 2019-03-12), a small normalized error is observed, ranging between -1.37% and +4.89%. In contrast to the previews two dates, the third date (2020-04-08) exhibits a larger normalized error, ranging from -8.65% to -1.99%. Moreover, all the indices undervalue the surface when compared to the High Spatial Resolution Image (HSRI), whereas in the previous two dates, except the MNDWI and SWI which exhibited undervaluation.

Table 8: Normalized differences between the High Spatial Resolution Image (HSRI) date surface and indices for the Lebna reservoir. The lowest differences between the water surface estimated by HSRI and the water surface estimated by spectral indices are highlighted in bold, while the highest differences are underscored.

HSRI Date	2017-08-30	2019-03-12	2020-04-08
Sentinel-2 Date	2017-08-29	2019-03-12	2020-04-05
Error between HSRI and Ground (%)	-0.41	-0.34	-5.5
Error between HSRI and AWEI (%)	1.53	1.64	-4.66
Error between HSRI and MBWI (%)	<u>4.89</u>	<u>3.47</u>	-1.99
Error between HSRI and MNDWI (%)	-0.27	-0.31	-6.35
Error between HSRI and NDVI (%)	3.72	1.71	-3.86
Error between HSRI and NDWI (%)	2.09	1.27	-4.32
Error between HSRI and SWI (%)	-0.73	-1.37	<u>-8.65</u>

Figure 7 provides an illustration of Pléiades, Sentinel-2 RGB, and the Modified Normalized Difference Water Index (MNDWI) images of Kamech on their closest common date. Unlike Lebna, conducting visual assessments for this reservoir proves challenging due to inadequate spatial resolution.

Figure 7: Pléiades, Sentinel-2 RGB, and the MNDWI images of Kamech

Examining Table 9 reveals that the indices and ground data-estimated surface exhibit a less favorable performance for Kamech than Lebna reservoir. Differences of water surfaces measured on the ground and the ones and by GoogleEarth analysis over the Kamech Reservoir range from 2.34 to 13.42% (2.10 ha to 3.52 ha, Table 19 of the Appendix). And differences of water surfaces by SI and by GoogleEarth analysis over the Kamech Reservoir range from 0.62% to 73.33% (in absolute value, Table 9). Indices like MNDWI and NDWI have the lowest normalized difference but manifest significant variability depending on the dates. This variability is observed across all indices, except for MBWI and AWEI, which consistently show high percentages. Another observation is that specific days witness superior performance across all indices. For instance, on October 27, 2018, the normalized difference is the smallest, ranging from -25% (MBWI) to -0.62% (MNDWI), in contrast to April 8, 2022, where the range spans from -73.33% (multiple indices) to -21.46% (MNDWI). On April 8, 2022, AWEI, MBWI, NDVI, and NDWI were to detect water, resulting in a normalized difference of -73.33% which percentage refers to the proportion of the HSRI compared to the reservoir size. This difference exists not only across indices but also among dates, a decision was made to conduct a spectral analysis between the dates October 27, 2018, and April 8, 2022 serving as a reference to decipher this phenomenon.

Table 9: Normalize difference between High Spatial Resolution Image (HSRI) surface and indices for Kamech. The lowest differences between the water surface estimated by HSRI and the water surface estimated by spectral indices are highlighted in bold, while the highest differences are underscored.

HSRI Date	2017-08-30	2017-10-10	2018-07-25	2018-10-27	2019-03-12	2022-04-08
Sentinel-2 Date	2017-08-29	2017-10-08	2018-07-25	2018-10-28	2019-03-12	2022-04-10
Error between HSRI and Ground (%)	10.76	-2.69	-2.34	7.72	8.44	13.42
Error between HSRI and AWEI (%)	-43.17	<u>-23.33</u>	-37.29	<u>-9.37</u>	-41.88	<u>-73.33</u>
Error between HSRI and MBWI (%)	-29.42	-21.88	<u>-43.75</u>	-25	<u>-74.58</u>	<u>-73.33</u>
Error between HSRI and MNDWI (%)	-29.42	-16.88	-21.46	-0.62	-24.79	-21.46
Error between HSRI and NDVI (%)	-18.38	-11.25	-43.13	-4.17	-25.21	<u>-73.33</u>
Error between HSRI and NDWI (%)	-12.13	-5.83	-35.83	-2.71	-17.08	<u>-73.33</u>
Error between HSRI and SWI (%)	<u>-43.58</u>	-16.25	-6.25	8.54	-58.96	-55.83

Figure 8a show there is possibly turbidity in contrast to 8b where the image does not seem to have anything out of the ordinary. Although with such low spatial resolution it is not possible to know if there is another factor that can effect the RGB image (such as aquatic vegetation). Figure 8c illustrates the spectra for the image acquired on 2018-10-28 where most indices exhibited favorable performance (difference from 0,62 to 25%, Table 9). In this graph, a typical spectral signature of water is observed across all points. This is confirmed by Band 3 being higher than Bands 5, 8, and 11, which were used in the normalized difference equation, resulting in positive values indicative of water pixels. Similarly, NDVI yielded negative values as Band 8 is surpassed by Band 4, indicating water pixels. The results of the multi-band indices (MBWI and AWEI) are more challenging to interpret due to their complex formulas. Nonetheless, a commonality between the two indices is their dependence on Band 3 having a significantly larger value than the rest of the subtracted bands in order to produce positive values something that happened for this day.

Figure Figure 8d depict the spectra of the four points for the second date. The spectra do not resemble a typical water profile. This evident firstly from the VNIR absorption (Band 5) that is less than the Red (Band 4) absorption, and secondly, there is high reflectance in the NIR part of the spectrum where water should ideally absorb nearly all radiation. Likewise to what was mentioned in the preceding paragraph, when Band 3 falls below the values of the other Bands 5, 6, 8, 11 used in the indices formula, it leads to the production of negative values, indicating the absence of water. Based on that a phenomenon such as aquatic vegetation or mud may be present and thus alters the spectral signature for that day.

Figure 8: Sentinel-2 RGB images of Kamech for the dates 2018-10-28 (a) and 2022-04-10 (b) with their respective spectrum view (c) and (d).

3.2 Analysis of multi-temporal water surface estimation

The water surface was then estimated for all sentinel-2 images, based on the 6 spectral indices presented in section 2.4.2 Spectral indices. The temporal results are divided to two sections, one for Lebna site and one for Berambadi. The two reservoirs from Lebna site are validate by the ground data estimated surface while the Berambadi reservoirs visually compared to water height data.

All the indices exhibit a similar trend over the Lebna reservoir (Figure 9), there are instances of unreasonably low estimations, particularly with MBWI and occasionally with AWEI. The MBWI tends to provide the lowest surface estimations while SWI tends to provide the higher surface estimations overall, although there are occasional deviations. MNDWI, NDWI, and NDVI display the most consistent and stable estimations. Despite occasional inconsistent estimations, the indices have small daily estimation variability. Visually inspecting the graph there is high correlation between the indices and the ground data. There are some instances were the ground estimation line is above or bellow the indices but this is happening mostly when the observations are not dense and create gaps.

Figure 9: Water surface (ha) estimated by the 6 spectral indices (coloured lines) and measured with daily ground data (black line) from January 2017 to October 2023 for the Lebna reservoir.

The spectral indices calculated for the Lebna reservoir demonstrate effective estimations of water surface and show strong correlation with R^2 values ranging from 0.86 to 0.98 (Table 10). MBWI less performs the least favourably, exhibiting the highest RMSE of 132.16 ha, an R^2 of 0.86 and a bias of -71.41 ha. In contrast, MNDWI performs the best, with an RMSE of 25.32 ha, an R^2 of 0.98 and a bias of 1.92 ha. MNDVI and SWI slightly overestimate with minimal margins of 1.92 hectares and 1.62 ha, respectively. In summary, all indices, except for MBWI and AWEI, demonstrate the ability to estimate the water surface within an acceptable margin of error and can be used as metrics for the uncertainty of water surface estimation.

Table 10: RMSE, R^2 and Bias calculated between ground data and spectral indices for the Lebna reservoir.

Indices	RMSE (ha)	RMSE (%)	R^2	Bias (ha)	Bias (%)
NDWI	41.21	5.72	0.94	-7.74	-1.08
MNDWI	25.32	3.52	0.98	1.92	0.27
NDVI	49.04	6.81	0.92	-12.72	-1.77
SWI	45.56	6.33	0.93	1.62	0.23
MBWI	132.16	18.36	0.59	-71.41	-9.92
AWEI	69.56	9.66	0.86	-25.9	-3.6

In contrast to Lebna reservoir, the water surfaces estimated by spectral indices from January 2017 to October 2023 are more chaotic (Figure 10). There are many periods where the spectral indices do not detect water while Ground data recorded water over the Kamech reservoir (Figure 10). NDWI (blue line is the index with the lower number of estimations of zero and near zero water surface. SWI (pink) seems to overestimate water surface estimations for multiple days but also have multiple underestimations while MBWI (brown) is the index with the lowest performance as shown in both Figure 10 and Table 11. In this reservoir the 6 spectral indices have significant daily

variability. Comparing the ground data estimation to the indices it is evident that all the indices underestimate the water surface as are well below the ground data estimation and do not follow the ground data estimate with precision.

Figure 10: Water surface (ha) estimated by the 6 spectral indices (coloured lines) and measured with daily ground data (black line) from January 2017 to October 2023 for the Kamech reservoir.

The 6 spectral indices calculated for the Kamech reservoir show very poor correlation with R^2 values ranging from 0.04 to 0.14 (Table 11). The table clearly indicates that MBWI and AWEI exhibit the poorest performance, while SWI also demonstrates suboptimal performance. On the other hand, NDWI and MNDWI showcase the best performance. Given the relatively low values of these metrics, direct comparisons may not yield meaningful insights. It needs to be noted that the comparison took into account the dates between October 2022 and May 2023 where the ground data was corrupted although this was a small part of the multi-year comparison. In general, the multitude of indices cannot be used as a metric of the water surface uncertainty for this reservoir as they do not correlate with the ground data and have a big negative bias.

Table 11: Kamech RMSE, R^2 and Bias between ground data and indices.

Indices	RMSE (ha)	RMSE (%)	R^2	Bias (ha)	Bias (%)
NDWI	1.56	32.5	0.14	-1.29	-26.88
MNDWI	1.88	39.17	0.04	-1.53	-31.88
NDVI	2.06	42.92	0.04	-1.78	-37.08
SWI	2.08	43.33	-0.1	-1.54	-32.08
MBWI	2.54	52.92	-0.02	-2.31	-48.13
AWEI	2.4	50	0	-2.11	-43.96

Figure 11 illustrates the temporal evolution of water surface estimation for the Berambadi site, featuring three reservoirs: Berambadi Dam, Kanegala River Tank, and Berambadi Temple Tank. Each reservoir is accompanied by water level data and ground photographs for specific days. Berambadi Dam, being the largest (47.94 ha), exhibits a discharging trend from January 2022 to September 2023 (Figure 11a), with all indices showing a similar pattern except, MBWI and AWEI

that present numerous inconsistent estimations. The same pattern is observed in Kanegala River Tank (Figure 11b). Both reservoirs generally align visually with the water level, except for the anomaly on April 21, 2023, where, despite near-zero observations by all indices, ground measurements two days later indicate the presence of water.

Berambadi Temple Tank (2.47ha) experiences inconsistent estimations among all the indices, and there is significant daily variability (Figure 11c). Additionally, the indices' estimations for this reservoir do not correlate with the water level. Similar to the previous reservoirs, there is no water detection for the observation on April 21, 2023 despite the ground measurement.

Figure 11: Water surface estimated by spectral indices (in ha, left y axis) and water level (in m, right y axis) from January 2022 to September 2023 for (a) Berambadi dam, (b) Kanegala River Tank and (c) Berambadi Temple Tank. The graphs includes photographs for specific days.

3.3 Analysis of seasonal water surface estimation

The spectral indices water surface estimation are not totally precise although can hint seasonal trends. For this reason a LOESS smoothing was applied to the indices estimation and the ground data estimation.

In Figure 12 similar with Figure 9 reveals a close resemblance between the indices and the ground data water surface estimation. The local maxima and minima of the indices' LOESS curves closely align with those of the ground estimate LOESS, except for MBWI, which only aligns in the first valley of July 2018. To investigate the effectiveness of LOESS in estimating charge and discharge patterns, Standard Deviation (SD) were computed both for estimated minimal and maximal surfaces and estimated dates of these minima and maxima. The fact that LOESS ground estimated dates of minimal and maximal surface extent fell before, within, or after the range of dates estimated from remote sensing data was also looked at. These analyses are presented in Tables 12 (statistics on seasonal minimal surfaces and associated dates) and 13 (same for maxima).

Figure 12: Lebna LOESS curves of the six indices and ground data estimation of water surface. Local maximal surfaces (peaks - red dots), representing the end of reservoir recharge, and minimal surfaces (valleys-black dots), corresponding to the end of reservoir discharge. Vertical black bars along the x-axis highlight the Sentinel-2 acquisition dates utilized for water surface estimation.

In the table depicting minimal surfaces, the estimation exhibits a substantial dispersion, verified by the high SD making the multiple indices' surface estimation using LOESS not useful. Conversely, the SD for the dates is relatively small, with instances of increased values occurring when the range expands due to MBWI acting as an outlier. The challenge with valleys explained by the range of the indices consistently lags behind the ground data date, albeit by less than a month.

Table 12: Statistics of the local minima on Figure 12 (black dots).

Minima	SD of indices water estimation (ha)	SD of indices minimal surface dates (days)	Range of minimal surface dates (days)	Date of minimal surface from ground data	Before/In/After
1	50	6.83	10	2018-07-22	After
2	59.3	20	90	2019-09-05	After
3	63.5	12.2	40	2021-09-24	After

Statistics of maximal extent estimations (Table 13) shows an equivalent pattern although the dispersion show to be smaller both on estimations of dates and surfaces. This is also true for the ranges and the ground data estimated date happen to be inside the range of the first two maximal surfaces. In the last maximal surface (February 2022) the ground data date is 7 days after the one of NDWI.

Table 13: Statistics of the local maxima on Figure 12 (red dots).

Maxima	SD of indices water estimation (ha)	SD of indices maxima surface dates (days)	Range of maxima surface dates (days)	Date of maxima surface from ground data	Before/In/After
1	21.2	10.2	25	2019-02-05	In
2	12.7	6.12	15	2020-02-22	In
3	11.7	9.17	25	2022-02-06	After

The figure above depicts the LOESS smoothed surface estimations of indices alongside the LOESS ground data estimation for the Kamech reservoir. In comparison to Figure 10, the LOESS graph (Figure 13) provides clearer insights, with more distinct and visible seasonal patterns as the noise is removed. Unlike Lebna, the indices for this reservoir do not align seamlessly throughout the temporal scale, but exhibit alignment predominantly in their maximal and minimal surfaces. An interesting observation is that in this reservoir each year has a maximal and minimal surfaces compared to Lebna making LOESS able to distinguish different patterns for different reservoirs in the same area. It is important to note that, at times, the LOESS values become negative. This anomaly is a result of the algorithm and these observations can be considered as 0.

Figure 13: Kamech LOESS curves of the six indices and ground data estimation of water surface. Local maximal surfaces (peaks - red dots), representing the end of reservoir recharge, and minimal surfaces (valleys-black dots), corresponding to the end of reservoir discharge. Vertical black bars along the x-axis highlight the Sentinel-2 acquisition dates utilized for water surface estimation.

The analysis of statistics is outlined in Table 14 and 15. The minimal surfaces table highlights that the SD of surface estimations is relatively high, considering the maximum size of the reservoir. The SD for the dates performs well overall, with exceptions observed in summer 2017 and 2019. In summer 2017, NDWI, and in summer 2019, SWI, can be considered outliers, as evidenced by their impact on the range. SWI influences the range in the fifth. The last cannot be validated due to corrupted data affecting the LOESS of the ground data. In general, all ground data estimations fall after the ranges of the indices, with the distance being relatively small. Exceptions are noted in the first and last valleys, where the estimations are less accurate.

Table 14: Statistics of the local minima on Figure 13 (black dots).

Minima	SD of indices water estimation (ha)	SD of indices minimal surface dates (days)	Range of minimal surface dates (days)	Date of minimal surface from ground data	Before/In/After
1	0.56	28	80	2017-11-24	After
2	0.5	3.76	10	2018-07-24	After
3	0.55	33.9	90	2019-09-07	After
4	0.51	16	40	2020-10-13	After
5	0.32	16.3	40	2021-09-03	After
6	0.52	17.7	35	20203-02-25	After

Table 15 of maxima surfaces exhibits a comparable trend to the minimal surfaces, with the distinction that both the SD of indices water estimation and SD of dates are smaller than those of the minimal surfaces. The ranges are also smaller, except for the third and last maximal surfaces, where SWI and AWEI act as outliers in the third, and NDWI acts as an outlier in the last. Furthermore, the last maximal surface lacks a corresponding value due to the impact of corrupted

data. Overall, the combined estimations of the maximals surfaces are in close proximity to the ground estimation, albeit consistently occurring slightly afterward.

Table 15: Statistics of the local maxima on Figure 13 (red dots).

Maxima	SD of indices water estimation (ha)	SD of indices maxima surface dates (days)	Range of maxima surface dates (days)	Date of maxima surface from ground data	Before/In/After
1	0.44	11.1	25	2018-04-18	After
2	0.42	2.74	5	2019-01-11	After
3	0.56	25.8	80	2020-02-23	After
4	0.3	11.1	35	2021-03-25	After
5	0.33	0	0	2020-07-20	After
6	0.3	36.8	100	-	-

For the Berambadi site reservoirs, it not feasible to accurately detect the maxima and minima (start of discharge and recharge) as there is not enough Sentinel-2 data from June to Dec every year (monsoon). For this reason a visual inspection of Berambdai Dam and Kannegala River Tank will follow along another reservoir (Kutunur Tank) will follow. Kutunur Tank is 30 ha reservoir in the downstream in the watershed with out ground data.

Berambadi Dam is located in upstream along the hydrological network. Except in the dry season of 2027, this reservoir had water along 2018 – 2023 (Figure 14b). AWEI and MBWI provides the lowest surface water values along 2018 – 2023, with more fluctuations than the other spectral indices. Kannegala River Tank (midle) presents a strong and quick decrease of water surface every dry season (Jan-May), without reaching a dry status except in June 2019 (Figure 14c). Like for Berambadi Dam, AWEI and MBWI provides the lowest surface water values along 2018-2023. Finally Kutunur tank (downstream) presents a strong and quick decrease of water surface every dry season (Jan-May), reaching a dry status every year around May (Figure 14d).

Figure 14: a) Location of 3 reservoirs along the hydrological network (in oranges). Water surface estimated by the 6 spectral indices and smoothed by the LOESS method for b) the Berambadi Dam (upstream), c) Kannegala River Tank (middle) and d) Kutunur Tank (downstream). Vertical black bars along the x-axis highlight the Sentinel-2 acquisition dates utilized for water surface estimation.

4. Discussion

In this research, the performance and ability of various multispectral RS indices to estimate inter-seasonal surface fluctuations for recharge and discharge patterns of small reservoirs in two semi-arid regions were assessed. The analysis revealed that the actual surface estimation accuracy was not optimal, and the feasibility of using multiple indices to quantify uncertainty was unsuccessful. However, the noise and frequently inconsistent estimations of the indices after being smoothed by LOESS were able to provide valuable information for temporal patterns of small reservoirs.

4.1 Analysis of the results

The comparison of water surface estimation at single dates compared to HSRI provided valuable insights into the individual performance of each index. The indices' surface estimations for the small reservoir (Kamech) exhibited higher daily variability and frequent incoherent estimations compared to the larger reservoir (Lebna), as observed in Table 8 and 9. In the spectral analysis of April 10, 2022, for Kamech (Figure 10), the anomaly of water spectra shows high reflectances over NIR part of the spectrum. This could potentially be attributed to aquatic vegetation, although confirmation would require ground information.

The multi-temporal comparison of indices water surface estimation to ground data surface estimations revealed that the water indices in the Lebna site performed well for the large reservoir (Lebna) but not for the small reservoir (Kamech), as indicated in Table 10 and 11. In the case of the Lebna reservoir, the indices exhibited a similar trend with each other and have low daily variability between them, with some irregular observations (Figure 9). This compared with their good statistic correlation with ground surface estimation make the multitude of indices suitable to serve as a metric for uncertainty. The same can not be said for the small reservoir (Kamech) where the indices yielded numerous irregular estimations and frequently failed to detect water (Figure 10). Moreover, they deviated significantly from the ground estimation, showing a substantial negative Bias ($\leq -26.88\%$) compared and very low correlation of $R^2 (\leq 0.14)$ as shown in Table 11.

The visual comparison of the three reservoirs (in Berambadi) water surface estimation by spectral indices and the water level demonstrated that the Berambadi Dam (large reservoir) and one small reservoir, Kannegala River Tank, performed well. However, the other small reservoir, Berambadi Temple Tank, exhibited poor correlation with water height, as illustrated in Figure 11. Due to the absence of ground surface data no statistical metrics was able to compute. Nonetheless, the visual comparison of water levels was promising for Berambadi Dam and Kannegala River Tank, while Berambadi Temple Tank did not exhibit a visually significant correlation with the water level. The latter reservoir was the smallest in this study, with a maximum surface area of 2.47 ha.

A constant observation across all the reservoirs was the underperformance of water detection of certain indices compared to others. More specifically MBWI and in a lesser extent AWEI had the worst water surface estimation performance and MNDWI and NDWI had better estimation performance. An explanation can be that both MBWI and AWEI are parametric indices originally designed for Landsat. With out any additional parameterization and thresholding for this study may made the indices less effective in water detection. To confirm that additional spectral analysis need to be conducted. SWI had an average performance and occasionally was more accurate than NDWI

(similar performance with MNDWI). That can be explain by the similarity of SWI and MNDWI where both indices use Band 11 (SWIR) that enhances the ability to detect turbid or shallow water (Singh et al., 2015). Although because SWI use Band 5 (VNIR) instead of Band 4 (Red) is more susceptible vegetation over MNDWI and this may decrees its performance.

The analysis of seasonal water surface estimation, conducted exclusively for the Lebna site, yielded intriguing results. The implementation of LOESS smoothing demonstrated its capability to translate the water surface estimations of the indices into a seasonal trend for both large and small reservoirs. The seasonal maximum recharge and seasonal maximum discharge estimated from the indices closely aligned with those from the ground data. In the Lebna reservoir, the peaks were found to be in close proximity to or within the range of the ground data peaks, while the valleys consistently preceded the ground data but remained very close, as illustrated in Table 12 and 13. Similarly, Kamech exhibited a comparable pattern, with both peaks and valleys of the indices consistently occurring a few days before the ground data. However, the first indices peaks and valleys did not align closely with the ground data peak and valley, as shown in Table 14 and 15.

A consistent observation for both reservoirs was that that specific minima and maxima of the indices were estimated closer to the ground data counterparts over some others. This phenomenon could be ascribed to the more frequent observation by Sentinel-2 in proximity to certain peaks or valleys compared to others that experienced fewer observations nearby. Another plausible explanation could be linked to the internal functioning of the LOESS algorithm or the parameter of span = 0.15 that been used in this study and its impact on the seasonal peaks or valleys. Both sites was the frequent misalignment of specific indices peaks and valleys with the other indices. In the case of Lebna, the peaks and valleys of MBWI consistently occurred well before those of the other indices. In Kamech, NDWI and SWI exhibited disparities, with NDWI points consistently leading and SWI points lagging behind those of the other indices. While the exact explanation for these discrepancies is challenging, it can be speculated that the suboptimal performance of MBWI with frequent incoherent estimations in Lebna contributed to this delay. In Kamech, the divergent behavior of SWI and NDWI, especially when NDWI failed to detect water, resulted in elevated water values for SWI and vice versa as shown in Figure 10 may lead to this latency behavior.

4.2 Limitations and impact

This research has potential for understanding the behavior of small reservoirs, it also reveals certain challenges. Water surface phenomena, including aquatic vegetation, glint, turbidity, and objects in the reservoir, can decrease the accuracy of water surface estimations (Khalid et al., 2021; Pan et al., 2020) and thus affect the ability to identify charge and discharge patterns in small reservoirs. The observation on April 21, 2023, where all indices failed to detect water for both Berambadi Temple Tank and Kannegala River Tank, despite contrary evidence from ground measurements, exemplifies this limitation. MNDWI and NDWI performed better than other indices, while MBWI and AWEI had the effect of outliers. Cloud contamination emerged as another limitation, especially during the wet season in Berambadi, leading to significant data gaps. Since the Berambadi site had ground measurements for less than a year, it was impossible to compare them with RS observations and define the seasonal pattern.

4.3 Remaining gaps/needs for further research

Understanding the seasonal variations in water surface is vital for gaining insights into the dynamics of small reservoirs. However, it is equally important to quantify the associated volume changes. While this study has illustrated the potential of multispectral RS in delineating seasonal trends, future research endeavors should capitalize on this information by integrating lake-specific rating curves to estimate volume fluctuations. Furthermore, there is a need for additional investigations to explore how parameterization and thresholding techniques can enhance the water detection performance of indices, thereby improving the capacity to estimate seasonal trends. As this was not happened in this study and the waters surface estimations was noisy. The idea to use LOESS smoothing was able to reveal these hidden seasonal patterns. Future endeavors need to research how this procedure can be used to automate the detection of seasonal patterns in small reservoirs. Overall the positive outcome of this study calls for more extensive research, involving a larger set of diverse small reservoirs and incorporating a detailed spectral analysis for specific dates characterized by irregular observations.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The outcomes of this study indicate that multitude of multispectral RS indices can accurately map the water surface of large reservoirs or estimating the uncertainty in water surface estimation but not of small reservoirs. However, they do exhibit potential in estimating seasonal patterns through the range of LOESS points representing maximum recharge and discharge. This conclusion is drawn primarily from a focused analysis in the Lebna site, where the indices alone failed to establish sufficient statistics metrics and correlation for ground data for the small reservoir (less than 5 ha), making quantification of uncertainty not feasible. Although, the identified seasonal trend using LOESS smoothing was able to be validated for both a large and a small reservoir.

This prompts the question of whether the accuracy of this LOESS methodology stems from the indices' performance in water detection, the density of satellite observations, or the impact of the LOESS algorithm. While offering potential insights into understanding small reservoir behaviour, further validation analyses are needed, using diverse studies and extended time periods.

In this study water surface data and seasonal LOESS surface graphs produced for all reservoirs inside Lebna and Berambadi watershed. Those can provide valuable information for further RS research and hydrologist. Moreover, this methodology holds promise for implementation with higher spatial and temporal resolution images such those from the Venus multispectral satellite.

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Appendix

The scripts of this study can be found in github repository:

<https://github.com/SotKech/S2Water>

Table 16: Lebna reservoirs and maximum size and IDs.

ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)	ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)
1	Lebna	720	7	Ben salem	1.48
2	Akrane	19.99	8	El Guitoun	2.17
3	Ain Soudan	9.41	9	Gbail	3.68
4	Gombar	25.35	10	Kamech	4.8
5	Errouiguet	17.98	11	No Name 11	1.32
6	El Hajia	1.21	12	Ennar	3.06

Table 17: Berembadi reservoirs and maximum size and IDs.

Inside watershed						Outside watershed		
ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)	ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)	ID	Reservoir Name	Size (ha)
1	Maddur Tank (NW)	1.62	26	Gopalapura Tank	1.3	15	No Name 15	0.45
2	Berambadi Dam	47.94	28	Motana katte	1.29	16	No Name 18	0.2
3	Channamallipura 1 (NW)	0.4	29	No Name 29 (Center)	1.52	17	No Name 17	0.07
4	Channamallipura 2 (NW)	1.09	30	Kutunur Tank	31.12	19	No Name 19	0.38
5	Channamallipura 3 (NW)	1.2	31	No Name 31 (Center)	0.54	27	Devarahalli Dam (SE)	24.28
6	No Name 6 (NW)	1.38	32	No Name 32 (Center)	0.26	36	Gopaldaswami Dam (SE)	15.21
7	Kunagahalli Dam (SW)	1.92	33	No Name 33 (Center)	0.76	38	No Name 38	0.52
8	Berambadi Temple Tank	2.47	34	No Name 34 (NE)	0.25	42	No Name 42	0.3
9	Gopaldaswamy Temple Tank (SW)	0.71	35	No Name 35 (NE)	0.27	45	Kallipura Tank (SE)	13.28
10	No Name 10 (NE)	1.09	37	Kaggaladundi Temple Tank (NW)	0.72	46	Forest Tank (SE)	18.14
11	No Name 11 (Center)	1.07	39	Maramma Temple-Tank (NE)	0.7	49	No Name 49	0.57
12	Kannegala Village Tank	3.68	40	No Name 40 (NE)	0.37	53	Kuruti katte	< 0.01
13	Kannegala River Tank	8.87	41	No Name 41 (SE)	0.42			

14	Honnegowdanahalli Tank (SE)	2.26	43	No Name 43 (NW)	0.11
16	Kunagahalli Tank (SW)	0.98	44	Belavina Katte	0.62
20	No Name 20 (NW)	0.23	47	No Name 47 (Center)	1.37
22	No Name 22 (SW)	0.35	48	No Name 48 (SE)	0.31
23	No Name 23 (SW)	0.26	50	No Name 50 (SW)	0.42
24	No Name 24 (SW)	0.55	51	Lakki Katte	0.29
25	Parvatana Katte	0.59	52	Navilugundi Kere	< 0.01

Table 18: Absolute differences between the High Spatial Resolution Image (HSRI) date surface and indices for the Lebna reservoir.

HSRI Date	2017-08-30	2019-03-12	2020-04-08
Sentinel-2 Date	2017-08-29	2019-03-12	2020-04-05
Error between HSRI and Ground (Abs.)	2.97	2.42	39.6
Error between HSRI and AWEI (Abs.)	-10.99	-11.79	33.52
Error between HSRI and MBWI (Abs.)	-35.2	-25	14.3
Error between HSRI and MNDWI (Abs.)	1.92	2.23	45.75
Error between HSRI and NDVI (Abs.)	-26.78	-12.32	27.77
Error between HSRI and NDWI (Abs.)	-15.04	-9.17	31.08
Error between HSRI and SWI (Abs.)	5.24	9.87	62.27

Table 19: Absolute differences between the High Spatial Resolution Image (HSRI) date surface and indices for the Kamech reservoir.

HSRI Date	2017-08-30	2017-10-10	2018-07-25	2018-10-27	2019-03-12	2022-04-08
Sentinel-2 Date	2017-08-29	2017-10-08	2018-07-25	2018-10-28	2019-03-12	2022-04-10
Error between HSRI and Ground (Abs.)	2.89	1.61	1.99	3.92	4.36	4.16
Error between HSRI and AWEI (Abs.)	0.30	0.62	0.31	3.10	1.94	0.00
Error between HSRI and MBWI (Abs.)	0.96	0.69	0.00	2.35	0.37	0.00
Error between HSRI and MNDWI (Abs.)	0.96	0.93	1.07	3.52	2.76	2.49
Error between HSRI and NDVI (Abs.)	1.49	1.20	0.03	3.35	2.74	0.00
Error between HSRI and NDWI (Abs.)	1.79	1.46	0.38	3.42	3.13	0.00
Error between HSRI and SWI (Abs.)	0.28	0.96	1.80	3.96	1.12	0.84